

INTERFACIAL MICROSTRUCTURE AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF C/C COMPOSITES

Kenichi Hamada*, Shinji Sato**, Hideo Tsunakawa*** and Akira Kohyama
Institute of Atomic Energy, Kyoto University

*: Research Fellow of the Japan Society for the Promotion of Science
Gokanosyo, Uji, Kyoto, 611 Japan

** : Department of Materials Science, The University of Tokyo

***: Engineering Research Institute, The University of Tokyo
Hongo, Bunkyo-ku, Tokyo, 113 Japan

ABSTRACT

Effects of heat treatment temperature (HTT) on interfacial microstructure and interfacial mechanical properties of carbon/carbon (C/C) composites are investigated. Formation and/or growth of graphite layers adjacent to fiber-matrix interface were detected by transmission electron microscopy (TEM). Ultra micro dynamic indentation test technique was developed and was applied to C/C composites and fiber push out tests were also carried out. In case of fiber push out, the indentation curve showed a plateau which was interpreted to correspond with fiber push out. Interfacial sliding strength, evaluated from the load at the plateau, was increased with increasing HTT above 2000 K.

INTRODUCTION

As a result of the recent efforts to refine carbon fibers and matrix precursor, mechanical properties of C/C composites have been successfully improved. The current goal is to optimize the interfacial mechanical properties to up grade the performance of C/C composites. The objective of this work is to investigate a correlation between interfacial mechanical properties and microstructure of C/C composites to meet the goal. In this paper, two researches are carried out. One is TEM inspection on changes of interfacial microstructure with increasing HTT. And the other is to develop a test technique for evaluating interfacial mechanical properties of C/C composites and to clarify its dependence on HTT.

Micro indentation test machine has been widely applied to a various kind of fiber reinforced materials to measure their interfacial mechanical properties in many studies [1-3]. But the authors can find quite a few studies about interfacial mechanical properties of C/C composites

Figure 1. Schematic flow of preparing push out specimen, specimen settings and shape of indenter tip.

utilizing indentation technique [4]. The newly developed ultra micro indentation test machine allows to locate the indenter with an accuracy of $0.5 \mu\text{m}$. This accuracy makes the apparatus possible to indent at the center of fibers with their diameters of about $10 \mu\text{m}$. Fiber push out tests were successfully performed with the apparatus under the condition with sufficiently thin specimen thickness. From load-displacement relations, interfacial shear stress was defined and was evaluated. Effects of HTT on the interfacial shear stress was discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Materials used were uni-directionally reinforced C/C composites. They were heat treated at several HTT from 1473 to 2773 K to change microstructure. Carbon fibers used were mesophase-pitch based fibers, and matrix precursor was a mixture of green coke and phenolic resin (a mixture with the ratio of 80/20). Their fiber volume fractions were 45.2 (1473 K) ~ 48.9 (2773 K) % and densities were 1.62 (1473 K) ~ 1.82 (2773 K) $\times 10^3 \text{ kg/m}^3$.

Specimens for TEM were prepared by dimple grinding and Ar ion milling, and were observed both parallel to and cross sectional to the fiber direction. Preparation of specimens for fiber push out test is shown in Fig. 1. C/C specimen was fixed at the center of acrylic pipe by resin. And next, the fixed specimen was sliced perpendicular to the fiber direction with about $200 \mu\text{m}$ thickness by low speed diamond saw. Then the thickness of sliced specimens were reduced under $100 \mu\text{m}$ by mechanical grinding and the pipe and resin were removed in acetone. Finally, the specimen was placed over a groove on a specimen holder, which was engraved by laser, and fibers located at the center of the groove were loaded by a diamond trigonal pyramid indenter tip. Both 100 and about $20 \mu\text{m}$ width groove were engraved to inspect groove width effects on indentation tests. The shape of diamond trigonal pyramid indenter tip is shown in Fig. 1 and the inclination angle of side triangle is 68 degrees.

Fiber push out tests were carried out by utilizing dynamic ultra micro indentation test machine. This machine measures the displacement of indenter tip with controlling loading speed. In this study, constant displacement speed tests were applied from 0 load to presetting maximum load by controlling loading speed. Under this setting, a rapid increase of displacement of indenter tip is supposed to indicate a rapid increase of displacement without load change on a indentation curve, and the indentation curves of actual pushed out fiber showed such aspects.

Figure 2. Cross section TEM images of C/C composites. (A) TEM image near interface. Arrow indicates observable interface. (B) Graphite layers grown between fiber and matrix. (C) Folding graphite structure of carbon fiber.

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CROSS SECTION ANALYSIS

As carbon matrices were readily milled and fragile than carbon fibers, many of the fibers at the edge of TEM specimens were dropped off, or most of the matrices near the interface were worn out. These difficulties of cross section specimen preparation suggested that the quite limited observable field, like a area pointed by the arrow in Fig. 2(A), was one of the most firmly stuck interface. As for these limited fields, growth of graphite layers adjacent to interface was observed as reported in previous works [5]. Such growth are considered to be enhanced by the compressive stress perpendicular to the fibers with matrix shrinkage in the process of heat treatment. And these layers had been grown into a fiber and a matrix shown in Fig. 2(B). These layers seemed to connect chemically the fiber and the matrix, and to be a origin of firmly sticking of this area. As for cross section image of fiber, Fig. 2(C) shows fold structure of

Figure 3. Microstructure changes of fiber-matrix interface with increasing HTT.
(t = specimen thickness)

graphite layers as reported in some studies [6]. These layers near fiber surface seemed to be connected partially with the graphite layers at interface and to be another origin of firmly sticking.

HTT DEPENDENCE ON MICROSTRUCTURAL CHANGES

As preparation of cross section TEM specimen, especially low HTT specimens, was difficult, HTT dependence of interfacial microstructure was inspected utilizing longitudinal specimen. Fig. 3 shows microstructural changes of interface with increasing HTT from 1873 K to 2273 K. Matrix adjacent to interface of 2273 K showed significant development of graphite structure than 1873 K. Both fiber and matrix of 2273 K also showed apparent enhancement of graphitization. Such significant matrix graphitization close to the interface was considered to be intensified by increasing matrix shrinkage with increasing HTT; that was supported by the fact that the fiber volume fractions and the densities of specimens become higher with increasing HTT. Although clear observation of the graphite layer growth into fibers and matrices was difficult from longitudinal direction, chemical connection between fibers and matrices seemed to become firm with emphasizing graphitization of fibers and matrices. As it should need larger shear stress to disconnect a firmly sticking fibers and matrices, high HTT specimen needs larger load for fiber debonding. But, for fiber pushing out, larger load may not necessarily need; because it should be the sliding force between fibers and matrices to affect the load for fiber pushing out. Microstructural inspection of mechanically disconnected interface should be also needed for total investigation of interfacial microstructure effective for both debonding and sliding of fibers.

Figure 4. Effects of specimen thickness and HTT on load-displacement of indenter tip curve.

Figure 5. SEM images of indented and protruded side of push out carbon fiber.

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Fig. 4 presents typical load-displacement on indenter tip curves (indentation curves) with 100 μm groove. Thick specimen examination showed only fibers push in shown in Fig. 5, and no fiber push out was observed. But some of indented fibers of enough thin specimens were protruded from the opposite surface shown in Fig. 5. All the push out fibers showed a plateau, where displacement increases without increasing load, on their indentation curves shown in Fig. 4. On the contrary, fibers without a plateau on their indentation curves were never protruded. These facts suggest that fiber push out turns out at this plateau, and the load at the plateau is needs for fiber push out. In this study, interfacial sliding strength is evaluated as following Eqn (1);

$$\tau_{is} = P / \pi Dt \quad (1)$$

where τ_{is} is interfacial sliding strength, D is the fiber diameter and t is the specimen thickness. Fig. 5 shows no trace on the indented carbon surface after testing. Therefore, thin gold layer was deposited by sputtering on the specimen surface to visualize the contact position of indenter tip.

Figure 6. Schematic image of deflected specimen with indentation test.

At the primary process of indentation test, only a load to penetrate the indentation tip into fiber should be needed. Under this assumption, there must be no difference between the indentation curves of thick and thin specimens. But the displacement of thin specimens were increased at a load than thick specimens, shown in Fig. 4. These results were explained by quite low elastic modulus of matrix than fiber. Schematically shown in Fig. 6, over groove part of thin specimen should be, different from the case of thick specimen, wholly flexed with indentation test. That makes the displacement to be increased by the flexural displacement. This explanation is supported by two results. One is the decrease of displacement difference between thick and thin specimen with increasing HTT. It is because the elastic modulus of matrix should be higher with increasing HTT and the flexural displacement should be decreased with increasing matrix modulus. The other is the decrease of displacement difference with reducing groove width. It is because the flexural modulus of specimen should become higher with decrease of flexural span. In addition, the displacement of thick specimen is decreased with increasing HTT. This change should mainly be supported by fiber modulus increase with increasing HTT, which was indicated by a investigation utilizing Raman spectrascopy [7].

Fig. 7 shows dependence of interfacial sliding strength on HTT with 20 μm width groove. At lower HTT than 2000 K, quite a little HTT dependence can be distinguished, and at higher HTT, interfacial sliding strength increases with increasing HTT. Here, the interfacial sliding strength is conventionally assumed to be determined by the following Eqn (2);

$$\tau_{is} = \mu\sigma_r \quad (2)$$

where μ is coefficient of sliding friction and σ_r is residual stress perpendicular to the fiber. As for the residual stress, both shrinkage of matrix during heat treatment and misfit of thermal expansion coefficient between fiber and matrix are dominant. Shrinkage of matrix should be enhanced with increasing HTT. On the other hand, not enough data about thermal expansion coefficient of carbon fiber, especially radial coefficient, and of carbon matrix, especially graphitized matrix adjacent to the fiber, have been obtained. With regard to carbon fiber, Saito *et al* [8] reported the radial thermal expansion coefficient of a polyacrylonitrile based carbon fiber was $8.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$, and showed no test temperature dependence from room temperature to 1000 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Sheaffer [9] reported that of a mesophase-pitch based carbon fiber was $12.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ (at room temperature). Concerning about carbon matrix, thermal expansion coefficient of a typical isotropic graphite material is $6.5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ (from 350 to 450 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, catalog data), and that of many graphite materials are reported to be increased with increasing test temperature from room temperature to 1000 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ [10]. As the authors can not find any data over 1000 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, it is difficult to discuss about the degree of thermal expansion coefficient misfit between fiber and matrix from over 2000 K HTT down to room temperature. But no test temperature dependence of thermal expansion coefficient of carbon fiber suggests the misfit from high HTT down to room temperature should not be large. Therefore, the total radial residual stress should be increased with increasing HTT. As for coefficient of sliding friction, the authors also can not

Figure 7. Dependence of interfacial sliding strength on HTT.

obtained and find any data about that between carbon fiber and carbon matrix. One of the next goal of this work is quantitative analysis of the resident stress and estimation of the sliding friction coefficient from Eqn (2).

As shown in Fig. 7, the interfacial sliding strength seems to be effected by the specimen thickness. But discussion of the specimen thickness dependence is difficult because different tendencies are shown at lower and higher HTT. The flexion of thin specimen becomes larger with decreasing the specimen thickness. Transformation of matrix around the indented fiber should increase and/or decrease the radial stress to fibers, and these stress effects on interfacial sliding strength. For more precise evaluation, quantitative analysis of these stress effects, or sophistication of test technique to prevent the specimen flexion and to eliminate the specimen thickness effects are needed.

One another potential mechanism is surface effects. The interface close to the ground and milled specimen surface was potentially damaged, and the sliding strength of such part of interface was considered to be small than the other sound part. Therefore, the interfacial sliding strength should not be estimated utilizing specimen thickness, t , should utilizing $t-\alpha$, where α was so-called free-edge correction constant [11]. SEM observation did not indicate any damage of interface, but such surface effect was a potential factor of specimen thickness effects.

CONCLUSIONS

Changes of interfacial microstructures and mechanical properties of C/C composites were investigated as a function of HTT. The conclusions can be summarized as follows.

1. Fiber push out examination of C/C composites were carried out by utilizing ultra micro dynamic indentation test machine. The interfacial sliding strength was evaluated from the load at a plateau of indentation curve.
2. Interfacial sliding strength showed little HTT dependence at lower HTT than 2000 K, but it was increased with increasing HTT at higher HTT. Enhanced shrinkage of matrix at higher HTT should be a main mechanism of this dependence.
3. Indentation curves were strongly effected by the flexion of specimen. Sophistication of test technique to prevent the specimen flexion and to eliminate the specimen thickness effects are necessary for more precise evaluation.

4. Growth of graphite layer into fibers and matrices were observed at the interface. This growth should stick fiber and matrix firmly. Graphitization of matrix adjacent to the interface was enhanced with increasing HTT, it should be enhanced by increasing radial stress with large shrinkage at high HTT.

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